

Pygeoweaver for FAIRable and Tangible Earth Science Workflow

Gokul Prathin Asamani
Center for Spatial Information Science and Systems
George Mason University
Fairfax, USA
gasamani@gmu.edu

Ziheng Sun
Center for Spatial Information Science and Systems
George Mason University
Fairfax, USA
zsun@gmu.edu

Abstract—Earth science research heavily relies on the productivity of the scientific community. However, this productivity is often hindered by inefficiencies and a lack of reproducibility in workflow composition and sharing. This is primarily due to the absence of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles in workflow and data management. This paper demonstrates the practical application of Pygeoweaver, a Python library for data pipeline management, to address these challenges and enhance research productivity in Earth data processing workflows. Using Pygeoweaver, researchers can optimize workflow design, simplify data retrieval, enable efficient analysis, and facilitate result visualization. This integrated approach promotes collaboration and ensures the reproducibility of research findings.

Keywords—Workflow; Sea surface temperature; Earth Science; FAIR

I. INTRODUCTION

Earth science community has witnessed a significant surge in available geospatial data, opening up unprecedented opportunities for researchers to gain valuable insights into a wide array of Earth processes. However, effectively harnessing this vast data pool poses substantial challenges, particularly in data retrieval, processing, and analysis. Due to geospatial data's diverse sources, formats, and scales, individual scientists often face time-consuming data retrieval and preparation tasks. For instance, researchers studying the impact of climate change on a specific region will have to integrate data from multiple sources, including satellite measurements, weather station records, and climate model simulations.

To address these challenges, scientific workflows have emerged as a vital solution. These workflows enable scientists to systematically manage data analysis, from data retrieval to analysis and visualization. They streamline complex data integration tasks and ensure that research processes are reproducible and efficient.

Within the ecosystem of workflow management for Earth science research, NASA's Earth Observing

System Data and Information System (EOSDIS) plays an essential role. EOSDIS is an extensive data management system, serving as the central repository for Earth science data gathered from NASA's satellites, aircraft, and field campaigns. Among its components, the Global Imagery Browse Services (GIBS) ensures swift access to satellite imagery, while EarthData Search empowers users with advanced data search and discovery capabilities.

In this context, Pygeoweaver emerges as an indispensable platform tailored to the needs of Earth scientists. Pygeoweaver, a Python library that acts as a user-friendly interface to the Java application Geoweaver, is purpose-built to simplify and streamline the management of data pipelines within a unified and accessible environment. What sets Pygeoweaver apart is its ability to seamlessly integrate into existing workflows, enabling researchers to coordinate data retrieval and processing tasks efficiently. It empowers scientists to execute all essential actions from a single, convenient location while meticulously documenting each step, execution logs, and the complete history of workflows and processes. Furthermore, Pygeoweaver promotes collaboration by facilitating the import and export of workflows as portable files, greatly simplifying the sharing and replication of research workflows.

II. PYGEOWEAVER

Pygeoweaver represents our innovation for research productivity, building upon the established Geoweaver foundation—an intuitive, user-centric scientific workflow management system [1]. It effectively addresses the challenges of research productivity and the adherence to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles in the context of workflow and data product development. It offers the distinct advantage of requiring minimal setup. Table 1 shows the comparison of Pygeoweaver to other mainstream workflow systems.

TABLE I. Comparison with other existing workflow systems

Features	Pygeoweaver	Argo	Airflow	Prefect
Streamlined Sharing and Collaboration	Supports easy sharing and collaboration.	Lacks streamlined sharing and collaboration.	Lacks streamlined sharing and collaboration.	Lacks streamlined sharing and collaboration.
Portable Workflows	Creates portable workflow zip files.	Does not support portable workflows.	Does not support portable workflows.	Does not support portable workflows.
Comprehensive Metadata	Provides comprehensive metadata management.	Does not provide comprehensive metadata.	Does not provide comprehensive metadata.	Does not provide comprehensive metadata.
Streamlined Deployment	Simplifies workflow deployment.	Limited streamlined deployment.	Does not offer streamlined deployment.	Does not offer streamlined deployment.
Graphical Workflow Editor	Offers a graphical workflow editor.	Does not provide a graphical editor.	Does not provide a graphical editor.	Does not provide a graphical editor.
Automatic History Recording	Automatically records workflow history.	Does not automatically record history.	Does not automatically record history.	Does not automatically record history.
Enhanced Reproducibility and Transparency	Enhances reproducibility and transparency.	Does not offer equivalent enhancements.	Does not offer equivalent enhancements.	Does not offer equivalent enhancements.
Remote and Distributed Execution Capabilities	Supports remote and distributed execution.	Does not offer remote and distributed execution.	Does not offer remote and distributed execution.	Does not offer remote and distributed execution.
Workflow Monitoring and Alerting	Supports workflow monitoring and alerting.	Limited workflow monitoring and alerting.	Offers workflow monitoring and alerting.	Offers workflow monitoring and alerting.
Real-time Data Processing and Analysis	Enables real-time data processing and analysis.	Does not focus on real-time capabilities.	Does not focus on real-time capabilities.	Does not focus on real-time capabilities.
In-browser Workflow Composition and Execution	Allows in-browser workflow composition and execution.	Does not provide in-browser composition.	Does not provide in-browser composition.	Does not provide in-browser composition.
Interactive Visualization and Analysis Tools	Supports interactive visualization and analysis tools.	Does not emphasize this aspect.	Does not emphasize this aspect.	Does not emphasize this aspect.
Collaborative Workspace for Workflow Development	Offers a collaborative workspace.	Does not have a built-in collaborative workspace.	Does not have a built-in collaborative workspace.	Does not have a built-in collaborative workspace.
Multi-platform Support (Local, Cloud, Distributed)	Provides multi-platform support.	Lacks support for multiple platforms.	Offers support for multiple platforms.	Offers support for multiple platforms.

Pygeoweaver is a solution that streamlines and simplifies data pipeline management, operating within a unified, user-friendly environment. It seamlessly integrates with existing workflows, allowing researchers to optimize data retrieval and processing tasks with heightened efficiency. Users can execute all essential actions from a singular, user-friendly interface while meticulously recording each

procedural step, execution logs, and the comprehensive history of workflows and processes. This capability simplifies collaboration and workflow replication by importing and exporting workflows in portable formats. It also serves as a tangible instrument for enhancing research productivity by leveraging intuitive APIs and Python library functionalities, enabling the design and execution of workflows with

greater efficiency. It can integrate diverse datasets and algorithms effectively, ensures research reproducibility, and promotes collaboration. Researchers benefit from streamlined workflow processes, reducing time expenditure, mitigating errors, and ensuring result reliability.

It aligns seamlessly with FAIR principles, underpinning the development of discoverable, accessible, and reusable workflows. Researchers can confidently contribute to the global scientific community by adhering to principles that enhance workflow discoverability and reusability. Pygeoweaver's architecture is characterized by its versatility. It hinges upon a robust set of API calls, enabling seamless communication between web browsers and Geoweaver. Further, this architecture supports various operating systems, including Windows, Linux, and MacOS. Such cross-platform compatibility renders Pygeoweaver adaptable and versatile across diverse research environments.

III. USE CASE: ANALYZING OCEANOGRAPHIC CHANGES USING NASA EARTH DATA IN CLOUD

Data acquisition and preparation involve accessing various data products from NASA's Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center (PO.DAAC) in the cloud, as described by Fournier [2]. This data retrieval is crucial for further analysis. In collaboration with the Jet Propulsion Laboratory and other research institutions, NASA used advanced satellite technology through the GRACE mission to investigate sea surface height and temperature changes since 1900. This mission accurately measured shifts in Earth's gravitational field [3], tracking changes in water storage, including ice melting and groundwater depletion, which impact sea level rise [4]. Using cloud computing, specifically the Earthdata Cloud provided by NASA, researchers analyzed GRACE mission data [5] effectively, enhancing our understanding of ocean changes [6-7].

Figure 1. The framework of Pygeoweaver

To showcase the practical application of the Earthdata Cloud and Pygeoweaver in ocean analysis, we've utilized open-source code developed by Jinbo Wang [8] and a tutorial provided by Openscapes for oceanographic analysis. This code is the foundation for constructing a comprehensive workflow using Pygeoweaver, enabling the seamless integration of multiple processes for specific ocean analysis tasks. The workflow comprises four distinct processes, each tailored for a particular task using Python. These processes include data retrieval, preprocessing, statistical analysis, and creating visualizations, including plots. By dividing the code into separate processes and harnessing Pygeoweaver's workflow management capabilities, we enhance the efficiency and reproducibility of oceanographic analysis.

IV. RESULTS

We have replicated the workflow provided by Dr. Jinbo Wang in the Openscapes tutorial, utilizing Pygeoweaver to construct a comprehensive workflow using Earth data in the cloud. The workflow code and the necessary dependencies and configurations are publicly available on GitHub [9].

Figure 2: Geoweaver Processes for Sea Surface Temperature Change Analysis Workflow

The entire workflow is packaged within a single zip file, simplifying its import and execution using Pygeoweaver. This eliminates the need for researchers to set up and configure individual processes manually, streamlining the workflow deployment. Upon importing the workflow zip file with Pygeoweaver, we seamlessly executed the entire analysis workflow. The data retrieval process accessed necessary data products from NASA's PO.DAAC was stored in the Earthdata Cloud, and subsequent steps ensured accurate plot generation.

Fig 3: SLA of 1993, 2000, 2010, 2022

V. CONCLUSION

Our findings emphasize Pygeoweaver's role in simplifying the integration of diverse data sources and processing algorithms. It provides a seamless interface for accessing and combining data from various origins, including satellite imagery, climate datasets, and geospatial databases. Researchers can efficiently incorporate these sources into their workflows, enabling comprehensive analyses and yielding valuable insights.

This paper presented a case study focused on analyzing sea level rise using Earth data in the cloud, particularly highlighting Pygeoweaver's utilization for accessing and analyzing NASA's Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center (PO.DAAC) data products. Building upon the work of Jinbo Wang's "Analyzing Sea Level Rise Using Earth Data in the Cloud" notebook, our study demonstrates the practical application and benefits of Pygeoweaver in working with geospatial data in a cloud environment. It showcases how Pygeoweaver simplifies data retrieval, workflow configuration, and result visualization using Python-based analysis tools and visualization libraries. The successful replication and execution of the workflow using Pygeoweaver highlights its potential to enhance research productivity and support reproducible analysis in Earth data science. Researchers can utilize Pygeoweaver to streamline the deployment of complex workflows, eliminating the need for manual configuration and ensuring the reproducibility of results. The availability of the workflow code, coupled with Pygeoweaver's user-friendly interface, makes it accessible for researchers to explore, adapt, and extend the analysis to address various research questions in climate change and environmental science.

The integration of Pygeoweaver empowers researchers to navigate the complexities of cloud computing, allowing them to access and process large-scale Earth data using Python efficiently. This paper highlights Pygeoweaver's capabilities, its role in

enhancing research productivity, and its practical implementation in Earth access workflows. We aim to accelerate scientific discoveries in Earth science and promote adopting cloud-based solutions for geospatial data analysis.

Through successful workflow replication and execution with Pygeoweaver, we underscore its potential to enhance research productivity and support reproducible analysis in Earth data science. Researchers can leverage Pygeoweaver to streamline complex workflow deployment, eliminating the need for manual configuration and ensuring result reproducibility. The availability of workflow code, coupled with Pygeoweaver's user-friendly interface, makes it accessible for researchers to explore, adapt, and extend analyses for diverse climate change and environmental science research questions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Sun, L. Di, A. Burgess, J. A. Tullis, and A. B. Magill, "Geoweaver: Advanced Cyberinfrastructure for Managing Hybrid Geoscientific AI Workflows," *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. 119, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.3390/ijgi9020119.
- [2] Fournier S., Willis J., Killett E., Qu Z. and Zlotnicki V.. 2022. JPL MEaSUREs Gridded Sea Surface Height Anomalies Version 2205. Ver. 2205. PO.DAAC, CA, USA. Dataset accessed [2023-06-23] at <https://doi.org/10.5067/SLREF-CDRV3>
- [3] Frederikse, Thomas, Felix Landerer, Lambert Caron, Surendra Adhikari, David Parkes, Vincent W. Humphrey, Sönke Dangendorf et al. "The causes of sea-level rise since 1900." *Nature* 584, no. 7821 (2020): 393-397.
- [4] Khan, Shfaqat Abbas, John Wahr, Michael Bevis, Isabella Velicogna, and Eric Kendrick. "Spread of ice mass loss into northwest Greenland observed by GRACE and GPS." *Geophysical Research Letters* 37, no. 6 (2010).
- [5] Tapley, Byron D., S. Bettadpur, Mo Watkins, and Ch Reigber. "The gravity recovery and climate experiment: Mission overview and early results." *Geophysical research letters* 31, no. 9 (2004).
- [6] Leuliette, Eric, and Laury Miller. 2009. "Closing the Sea Level Rise Budget with Altimetry, Argo, and GRACE." *Geophysical Research Letters* 36 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008gl036010>.
- [7] Luthcke, Scott B., H. Jay Zwally, Waleed Abdalati, David D. Rowlands, R. D. Ray, R. S. Nerem, F. G. Lemoine, J. J. McCarthy, and D. S. Chinn. "Recent Greenland ice mass loss by drainage system from satellite gravity observations." *Science* 314, no. 5803 (2006): 1286-1289.
- [8] Jinbo Wang, Ed Armstrong, Ian Fenty, Nikki Tebaldi, Jack McNeils, Jonathan Smolenski, Stepheny Perez, Catalina Oaida, Mike Gangl. (2022). *Analyzing Sea Level Rise Using Earth Data in the Cloud*. Retrieved from https://github.com/betolink/the-coding-club/blob/main/notebooks/Earthdata_webinar_20220727.ipynb
- [9] Earth-Artificial-Intelligence. "Earth-Artificial-Intelligence/Earth_data_cloud_clinic_geoweaver." *GitHub*. Accessed June 27, 2023. https://github.com/earth-artificial-intelligence/earth_data_cloud_clinic_geoweaver.